
CUSTOMER PERCEPTION AND CONSUMPTION OF MADE IN NIGERIA PRODUCT IN CROSS RIVER STATE

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Abstract

The researchers examine the effect of customer perception on consumption of made in Nigeria products in Cross River State. The study was born out of the fact that inclination of Nigerians to foreign goods is both alarming and disturbing especially when considering its effect on the local industries and the economy at large. The main objective of the study was to investigate the influence of consumption of made in Nigeria products in Cross River State. The study was burn out of Nigerians inclination to foreign products. The researcher adopted survey design as the main research design. The study was conducted in Calabar, Cross River State. 11 retail outlets were selected for the study. Structured questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection, the sample made up of 296 respondents across the retail outlets. Simple linear regression was used to analyze data from the field. The result revealed that the proxies of customer perception influences consumption. The researcher concluded that customer perception can directly affect consumption especially as it concerns made in Nigeria products and further recommend that Manufacturers should ensure that their brands and products are not prone to complications, dents, fading, and losing colours to enhance the trust of their customers.

Keywords: Customer, Perception, Consumption, Made in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The way customers perceive a product plays a vital role in his/her decision-making process. The view and mindset of the customer about a product to a large extent can determine the outcome of any marketing campaign or effort. Customer perception is a key ingredient in marketing campaigns and consists of a diverse collection of incentive tools, mostly short-term, designed to stimulate quicker or greater purchase of particular goods or services by consumers (Vignesh and Balaj, 2020). The frame of any individual's perception affects the way he interprets the world around him. It is important to note that two consumers may never have the same perception about a particular product, and this is often because their needs, wants and preferences, emotions are not the same. The perceptions of customers are very important to business operators and marketers because it determine their level of success, growth, and sustainability. Consumer perception refers to the awareness consumers have about a brand and their impressions or opinions about the brand along with its products and services. Consumer perception does more than impact on individual's purchase decision, it can shape the long-term relationship between the consumers and brands and because of this, every touch point between a company and its consumers should strive to affect customer perception positively to result in higher customer retention rates (Udonde, 2023).

One of the best ways a country can advance the standard of living of its citizens is to encourage the consumption and patronage of locally-made product and also formulate policies and standards that discourage total dependence on the importation of goods and services. Made-in-Nigeria products have been in existence even before colonization. Made in Nigeria products are those products that are manufactured in Nigeria by manufacturing companies domiciled in Nigeria (Enyia and Emelah, 2018). These products include fabrics, shoes, bags, accessories, cars, rice and others. From inception, there have been goods locally processed in Nigeria. However, these products were given recognition in the early 60s when Aba-based local entrepreneurs started imitating and producing shoes that could be likened to imported ones. The Made-in-Nigeria exhibition aimed to create a sense of awareness for the manufacturing industries in Nigeria so that their products could be patronized like those of advanced countries that are imported into the country. Over the years, Nigeria's manufacturing sector has been afflicted with intermittent power supply, huge scale under-use of manufacturing capability, and a poor and unhealthy customer patronage of locally made products (Iyiola *et. al*, 2018).

Coupled with all these problems is the resounding assertion of extant literature that after many years of exposure to high-quality goods from foreign manufacturers and strong customer relationship. Oladele and Arogundade (2011) observed that a strong relationship has developed between Nigerian consumers and imported brands, with a noticeable reluctance to embrace locally produced alternatives. Iloani (2017) further noted that consumer confidence in Nigerian-made products significantly declined in the final quarter of 2015, dropping from -3 to -1.9. Additionally, an analysis revealed a decline in business confidence among entrepreneurs, with the figure falling from 8.3% at the end of 2016 to 6.6% in the first quarter of 2017. These findings suggest that there is a negative shift in consumer perceptions towards locally produced goods in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The preference of Nigerians for foreign products is both concerning and troubling, especially when considering its impact on local industries and the broader economy. A prevailing belief among Nigerians is that domestic goods such as fabrics, shoes, bags, and

other fashion accessories are inferior to imported products in terms of quality, durability, and value. This perception has led some local manufacturers to falsely claim foreign origins or labels for their products in an attempt to maintain market relevance. Many Nigerians hold the view that products from outside the country are superior to those produced domestically. This mindset has hindered the growth and sustainability of Nigeria's manufacturing industries.

To address this issue, it is essential to critically examine consumer perceptions of Made-in-Nigeria products. The public's attitude toward locally produced goods has not been fully explored, and understanding this is vital. It appears that the perception of a product's country of origin significantly influences consumer consumption patterns. Negative perceptions, in particular, have a profound effect on consumer behavior and purchasing decisions. In light of these concerns, this study was conducted to investigate how customer perception influences the consumption of Made-in-Nigeria products in Cross River State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of customer perception on consumption of made in Nigeria products in Cross River State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the influence of perceived quality on consumption of made in Nigeria product
- ii. Examine the effect of Perceived globalness on consumption of made in Nigeria product
- iii. Ascertain the influence of perceived uniqueness on consumption of made in Nigeria product

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Perceived quality has no influence on consumption of made in Nigeria product in Cross River State

H₀₂: Perceived globalness does not affect consumption of made in Nigeria in Cross River State

H₀₃: Perceived uniqueness does not have an influence on consumption of made in Nigeria product in Cross River State

Research Questions

- i. Does perceived quality influences consumption of made in Nigeria product in Cross River State?
- ii. Does perceived globalness affect consumption of made in Nigeria product in Cross River State?
- iii. Does perceived uniqueness influences consumption of made in Nigeria product in Cross River State?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Overview of Customer Perception

Perception can be understood as the process through which an individual selects, organizes, and interprets sensory information (Enyia & Emelah, 2018). This implies that an

individual's perception framework influences how they interpret the world around them. According to Enyia and Emelah (2018), two customers can never share the same perception of a particular product, as their needs, desires, and preferences often differ. Customer perception holds significant importance for business owners because it directly impacts their success, growth, and sustainability. Thiruvencatraj and Vetrivel (2017) define customer perception as the way consumers form opinions about a product, based on conclusions drawn from various factors such as price, the perceived image of the country of origin, uniqueness, perceived risks, and overall experience.

The Business Dictionary (2015) describes consumer perception as a marketing concept that reflects a consumer's awareness, impression, or understanding of a company or its products. Perception is one of the key psychological factors influencing consumer purchasing decisions. Due to the inherent subjectivity in perception, individuals interpret external messages in different ways (Kotler & Armstrong, 2011). This subjectivity means that individuals process environmental stimuli differently. Influenced by their perceptions, consumers are more likely to purchase products that offer the highest perceived value to them. In essence, consumers tend to select products that align best with their positive perceptions.

Process of Perception

Madichie (2012), outlines the process of perception as follows:

Exposure: Exposure occurs when a stimulus enters the range of an individual's sensory receptors—such as sight, smell, or touch. Consumers may focus their attention on certain stimuli while completely disregarding others, or they may intentionally ignore specific messages.

Attention: Attention refers to the level of cognitive effort devoted to processing a particular stimulus. Consumers frequently experience sensory overload, where they encounter more information than they are able to process. From a marketing standpoint, consumers are often inundated with marketing stimuli from various commercial sources, creating an increasingly competitive environment for their attention.

Interpretation: Interpretation is the process by which we assign meaning to the sensory stimuli we encounter. Since individuals differ in the types of stimuli they perceive, the meanings they attribute to these stimuli also vary. Two people may witness or hear the same event, yet their interpretations can differ dramatically depending on their expectations of the stimulus. The meaning we assign to a stimulus is influenced by the schema—essentially a set of beliefs—through which we interpret it. Identifying and activating the appropriate schema is critical in marketing, as it determines the criteria consumers will use to assess a product, package, or message.

Consumer Perceptions and the Affecting Factors

•Pricing of a Product: The price of a product significantly influences consumer perception. While most consumers prefer affordable or reasonably priced items, there exists a segment of sophisticated and discerning consumers who view products priced lower than alternatives with skepticism. These consumers often perceive lower-priced products as "cheap" and of inferior quality,

even if they are of comparable quality to higher-priced options. Therefore, pricing should be an integral part of a broader marketing strategy. Through effective marketing, even budget-friendly products can be presented as high-quality, offering value at a competitive price.

•Quality of a Product:

The perceived quality of a product or service plays a crucial role in consumer perception. This includes factors such as the product's functionality, durability, and reliability in meeting consumer expectations. While marketing efforts can significantly shape consumer perceptions of quality, word-of-mouth communication about a product's quality can be equally influential and spreads rapidly among consumers.

•Branding and Packaging of a Product:

The adage "first impressions are the best impressions" is particularly relevant in shaping consumer perceptions at the point of purchase. A product's packaging, designed to showcase its quality and appeal, plays a critical role in how it is perceived. Additionally, branding messages such as "reliable," "long-lasting," or "tough" can greatly enhance the product's perceived value. Businesses often conduct market research to understand consumer preferences and perceptions, which helps in promoting products and services that align with consumer demands.

•History and Reputation:

The history and reputation of a company and its products are pivotal in shaping consumer perceptions. Established businesses with strong reputations are generally preferred by consumers, while new products tend to be approached with more caution, often influenced by public opinion and reviews. A company's reputation both online and offline can significantly impact consumer trust. Negative reviews or associations with unethical practices can have long-lasting detrimental effects on a company's performance.

•Country Image:

Country image refers to the associations consumers have with products from a particular country, shaped by their perceptions and beliefs about the country of origin. It encompasses the reputation, stereotypes, and characteristics that consumers attribute to products from that country. This image is influenced by factors such as representative products, national traits, economic and political context, history, and cultural traditions.

PROXIES OF CUSTOMER PERCEPTION

Perceived Quality

Perceived quality refers to a customer's evaluation and judgment of a product's overall excellence and superiority, though it is distinct from the actual quality of the product itself. Rezvani (2012) defines perceived quality as the customer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of a product. According to Salim and Rodhiah (2022), perceived quality is a form of consumer assessment based on the perceived benefits of the products and services offered. The quality of the customer experience plays a significant role in shaping purchasing habits and encouraging widespread consumption, even in highly competitive markets with numerous similar alternatives (Mainardes et al., 2019). This suggests that perceived quality reflects the consumer's overall judgment of a product's excellence or superiority.

Perceived quality encompasses the consumer's estimation of the added value a product or brand offers in various aspects, such as marketing communications, product pricing, brand awareness, brand loyalty, and market-driven perceptions of quality. It is important to note that perceived quality is not synonymous with the actual quality of a product but rather represents how consumers assess a product or service from a business perspective (Tuan & Rajagopal, 2017). Furthermore, Tuan and Rajagopal (2017) proposed that factors such as distribution channels, brand image, country of origin, price, and certifications can influence perceived product quality.

Perceived Globalness

Perceived globalness refers to the degree to which a brand is viewed as a global entity by consumers, indicating that it operates in multiple markets worldwide (Gu *et al.*, 2022). This concept explains how consumers perceive a brand as not only present in local markets but also in international markets. According to Zhou (2016), perceived brand globalness occurs when consumers recognize a brand as being marketed in various countries and widely acknowledged as a global brand in those regions. Dimofte *et al.* (2010) further highlighted that perceived globalness varies among consumers, largely shaped by their brand knowledge and experiences. Brands perceived as global often have a strong global identity, as they allow consumers to engage with global consumer culture (Xie *et al.*, 2015).

As a result, consumers may view global brands as superior to local brands, often choosing them even if the product quality or value does not necessarily surpass that of local alternatives. To assess perceived brand globalness, Steenkamp *et al.* (2003) developed a three-item measurement, which has been widely adopted by scholars such as Özsomer (2012) and Sichtmann and Diamantopoulos (2013). These three items measure the general recognition of a global brand, consumers' intention to buy global brands, and the global availability of the brand.

Perceived Uniqueness

Zhou (2016) defines perceived uniqueness as the extent to which consumers believe a brand stands out from its competitors. A brand that lacks a distinct identity may find itself at a disadvantage in a highly competitive market. In today's globalized environment, one of the major challenges for marketers is to differentiate their brands from others by emphasizing uniqueness. Ye *et al.* (2012) similarly describe perceived brand uniqueness as the consumer's ability to distinguish one brand from another based on personal perceptions and emotional responses. From these perspectives, uniqueness is viewed as a vital brand attribute that influences consumer decision-making.

Consumers are generally more willing to pay a premium for products they perceive as unique. In contrast, brands with generic or similar features tend to attract less attention. Unique products have a higher potential to quickly capture consumer interest. Moreover, many consumers desire a sense of individuality, which they may seek to express by purchasing exclusive or limited-edition items. Those with a strong need for uniqueness tend to be more discerning and are particularly drawn to rare or distinctive offerings in the market.

Overview of Consumption

Consumption encompasses a wide range of human activities and refers to the various stages involved in utilizing goods and services for daily living. It is commonly understood as the use of goods and services to satisfy consumer needs and desires. As a central aspect of everyday life, consumption shapes individual behaviors and routines, with the values, meanings, and implications of what we consume playing an increasingly significant role in both social and personal experiences. Roach et al. (2019) define consumption as the process through which goods and services are ultimately used by individuals.

According to Firat *et al.* (2013), consumption is shaped by consumer purchasing decisions and represents a combination of behaviors directed toward the utilization of economic goods. However, consumption extends beyond mere purchase; as Hartmann (2013) asserts, it also includes the appropriation, use, enjoyment, appreciation, and experience of both tangible and intangible items ranging from products and services to ideas, information, performances, and atmospheres serving a variety of purposes.

Overview of Made in Nigeria Product

Made-in-Nigeria goods refer to products that are produced within the country, either entirely or in part, using locally sourced materials. As stated by Enyia and Emelah (2018), these are goods manufactured by firms operating within Nigeria. The production of indigenous goods has existed since the nation's early history, but greater recognition was given to these products in the 1960s, particularly when local entrepreneurs in Aba began producing footwear modeled after imported varieties. Over the years, the Nigerian government has actively promoted the development of local industries as a strategy for economic growth and industrialization. In response, manufacturers especially those within the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) sector have produced a wide range of consumables, including fast-moving consumer goods. The manufacturing and promotion of made-in-Nigeria products have significantly contributed to the country's economic development by creating domestic industrial linkages essential for sustainable growth. The government has also increasingly relied on the private sector to drive its industrialization agenda (Liman, 2015).

Challenges in Marketing Made-in-Nigeria Products

According to Liman (2015), several challenges continue to hinder the effective marketing and distribution of made-in-Nigeria goods:

- 1. Insufficient Investment Capital:**

A persistent lack of access to financial capital undermines the growth of marketing initiatives. Although some policies mandate banks to allocate a portion of their profits to support small businesses, compliance has been low, and the stringent conditions attached to available funds make it difficult for SMEs to benefit.

- 2. Poorly Coordinated Business Strategies:**

Many local manufacturers face difficulties competing in export markets due to substandard products and a lack of knowledge regarding international marketing strategies and networks.

3. **Weak Institutional Support:**
There is a lack of a structured institutional and administrative framework to assist and sustain local producers. Even where technological or intellectual resources exist, they are often poorly managed or underfunded.
4. **Political and Social Instability:**
Frequent governmental changes and an unstable political environment discourage investment and disrupt the marketing of locally produced goods.
5. **Limited Competitiveness:**
Local products struggle to compete even in domestic markets due to the influx of cheaper, technologically superior imports from more advanced economies.
6. **Inadequate Equipment:**
The machinery required for production often needs to be imported at high costs, with unpredictable delivery times and a dependence on costly expatriate expertise.
7. **Lack of Process Technology:**
The absence of proprietary technologies, designs, and patents leads to additional financial burdens such as royalty payments and technology transfer fees.
8. **Failure to Meet International Standards:**
Nigerian manufacturers often struggle to comply with stringent quality and environmental standards imposed by developed nations, which are sometimes perceived as subtle trade restrictions.

Figure1: Conceptual Framework on Customer Perception and Consumption of Made in Nigeria Product

Source: Researchers' Model (2023)

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the **Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)**, developed by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. The theory posits that an individual's behavior is primarily guided by their behavioral intention to engage in a particular action. This intention, in turn, is influenced by two key components: the individual's **attitude** toward the behavior and the **subjective norms** surrounding it. Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) define subjective norms as the perceived social pressures or expectations from important individuals or groups in one's life regarding whether or not to perform a given behavior. The TRA is commonly expressed through the equation:

Behavioral Intention = Attitude + Subjective Norms

This theoretical framework is highly relevant to the present study, as it provides insight into how consumer perception is shaped—particularly in relation to their consumption behavior. It highlights the role of both personal evaluations and perceived social influences in shaping consumer intentions and actions.

Empirical Review

Enyia and Emelah (2018) explored the impact of product perception on the patronage of Made-in-Nigeria goods, aiming to examine the relationship between consumer perception and purchasing behavior. The study involved the administration of 100 questionnaires to staff and students of the University of Port Harcourt. Results revealed that most null hypotheses were rejected, except the one that tested the relationship between the behavioral component of perception and consumer patronage. It was concluded that consumers, particularly regarding high-priced items, have not yet developed a strong inclination towards locally manufactured goods. However, there is greater acceptance of agricultural commodities such as garri, tomatoes, onions, and cassava flour. The study recommended that reorientation of public perception should be prioritized through government intervention, academic contributions, and individual efforts.

Kitavi (2022) investigated the influence of consumer perception on mobile phone purchase intentions in Nairobi County, Kenya. The study examined how aspects like product perception, pricing, perceived quality, and consumer expectations impact buying decisions. Using a survey design and a sample of 400 participants selected through convenience sampling, data were analyzed with a binomial logistic regression model. Findings demonstrated that all studied variables significantly influenced purchase intention. The researcher recommended that manufacturers and regulatory bodies prioritize the incorporation of cutting-edge features and longer battery life in mobile phones to enhance customer attraction and satisfaction.

In another study, Osio and Orubu (2018) examined customer perceptions of online shopping in Nigeria. The study aimed to determine how internet users engage in e-commerce, particularly with clothing, electronics, and accessories. A total of 300 questionnaires were randomly distributed, and data were analyzed using percentages and variance analysis. The study concluded that customer service quality including order tracking, security assurances, and warranties is critical to improving consumer trust and online shopping experience.

Chukwu *et al.* (2020) focused on the influence of consumer value on behavioral patterns toward Made-in-Nigeria products in Rivers State. Utilizing a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 335 respondents across the 23 local government areas in the state. The study employed SPSS version 21.0 for multiple regression analysis. Results showed that perceived consumer value had a statistically significant but moderate impact on purchasing behavior. The researchers recommended that marketers increase their understanding of consumer values and align their strategies accordingly to encourage consistent patronage.

Similarly, Nyarunda (2016) conducted a study on consumer attitudes and preferences toward imported versus locally-produced apparel in Nairobi County. The study employed a stratified multi-stage sampling technique and analyzed data from 322 government employees. Findings indicated that there were no substantial differences in the criteria used by consumers when selecting apparel. The study emphasized the need for improved quality, durability, and product differentiation in local apparel to enhance competitiveness against imported alternatives.

Salim and Rodhiah (2022) examined the relationship between perceived quality, customer satisfaction, corporate image, customer experience, and customer loyalty using a sample of 100 LINE Webtoon app users in Jakarta. Data were analyzed through structural equation modeling (SEM) using SmartPLS. The findings revealed that perceived quality and customer experience significantly affect customer loyalty, whereas customer satisfaction and corporate image did not show a significant influence. The authors concluded that enhancing perceived quality and customer experience is crucial for building brand loyalty.

Ekanem *et al.* (2020) assessed consumer perception and acceptance of locally-produced rice in Akwa Ibom State. The study utilized a multi-stage sampling technique to select 340 respondents. Analysis using means, standard deviation, and rankings indicated a high level of positive perception, with local rice considered nutritious, affordable, and widely accessible. The researchers concluded that such perceptions increase product acceptability and recommended improvements in quality, packaging, advertisement, and branding to boost patronage.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher adopted survey design as the main research design. This is because survey design allows information to be gathered from a sample of people or organizations by the use of questionnaire.

Study Area

Calabar which is the capital of Cross River State in the South-South region of Nigeria was adopted as the study area. The proximity of the Area of study to the researcher eased the collection of needed data within the time frame of the study. Calabar is made up of two local Government Areas namely Calabar Municipality and Calabar South. It has an area of 406 square Kilometers (157 sqmi) and a population of 371,022 as at 2006 census.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the persons that were encountered at the major super market and vendors at the time of this study. This was irrespective of the demographic variables or social status of the respondents. Since it was not possible to have a clear figure of people in this category, the population of the study was treated as infinite.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size of this research was determined using the Top-man Formula for infinite population. The adoption of this Formula is to enable us get a sample size for the study which has an unknown population record of daily customers.

Thus, to arrive at an appropriate sample size for the study, a pilot study was carried out, using the research questionnaire on 20 selected customers that were encountered by the researcher at the super market. The strongly agree and agree responses to the questions allowed the researcher to generate values for 'P' (positive). On the other hand the strongly disagree and disagree responses allowed the researcher to generate values for 'Q' (negative), for the Top-man formula. To determine the sample size, the formula was applied as follows;

$$n = \frac{z^2(p \times q)}{e^2}$$

Where;

- n = required sample size
- z = the value of Z-score associated with the degree of confidence i.e. 95% confidence level, being 1.96 from the Z-score table.
- p = the percentage of positive response expressed as decimal
- q = (p-1) the percentage of negative response expressed as decimal
- e = Acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

Thus;

- Z = 1.96² i.e. 3.8416
- p = 22 i.e. 0.74
- q = 8 i.e. 0.26
- e² = 0.05² i.e. 0.0025

$$n = \frac{3.8416 (0.74 \times 0.26)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 (0.1924)}{0.0025} = \frac{0.73912384}{0.0025} = 295.64 \text{ i.e. } 296$$

Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the super markets and respondents for this study. This sampling technique was adopted due to the need to access the type of information and data needed for this study from the target respondent.

Table 1. List of Selected Super Market/Vendours in Calabar Metropolis Selected for the Study

S/N	Name of Super Market/Retail Store in Calabar Metropolis	Location
1.	Spar Calabar	Mary Slessor Avenue
2.	Lu Gold store	Mary Slessor Avenue
3.	44 Shopz	170 Murtala Mohammed Highway, Calabar
4.	Adorn and Glow	GRA Phase 1, Federal Housing Road, Calabar
5.	Audacious Calabar Mall	Mary Slessor Avenue, Barrack Road
6.	Big Qua Shopping Complex	Big Qua Road, MCC Road, Oqua Street, Calabar
7.	Calabar Online Watch Store	74A NdidemUsangIso Road, Calabar
8.	Classic Imports and Gift Shop	Shop H7 Akim Market, Akim Qua Town, Calabar,
9.	HQ Shop	No. 1B Custom Line, Federal Housing Estate Phase 2 off, Old Odukpani Road, Calabar
10.	O & E Plaza	No. 9 Foster Street, Calabar, Cross River
11.	Onyx Plaza	26 Ediba Road After Ecobank by Marian Market, Big Qua Town, Calabar,

Sources of Data

The main source of data for this study was primary data. This primary data was collected directly from the customers at the different super markets in calabar.

Data Analysis Techniques

Simple linear regression analysis was used to examine the extent of the relationship that exist between the predictor variables (perceived quality, perceived globalness, perceived uniqueness) and the criterion variable (consumption). The four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Model Specification

Consumption was estimated as a direct function of some customer perception proxies.

This can be expressed in functional equation form as in Equation 1

$$Y = F (X_1, X_2, X_3,) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Recoded to represent the variables, it is presented as;

$$C= F (Pq, Pg, Pu) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The simple regression model representing the relationship that exists between each independent variables ($X_1, X_2, X_3,$) and the dependent variable (Y) was expressed in the form:

$$H_{01}: Y = a_0 + b_1x_1 + e \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

$$H_{02}: Y=a_0 + b_2 x_2 +e \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$H_{03}: Y = a_0 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Equation 5

To represent the variables in use, the simple linear regression equations were presented as:

$$H_{01}: C = a_0 + b_1Pq + e$$

$$H_{02}: C = a_0 + b_2Pg + e$$

$$H_{03}: Mp = a_0 + b_3Pu + e$$

Where: C(Y) = Consumption
 Pq(X₁) = Perceived quality
 Pg(X₂) = Perceived globalness
 Pu(X₃) = Perceived uniqueness
 e = error term

The above estimated equations are linear function which was used in testing the model separately.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A total of two hundred and ninety six (296) copies of questionnaire were distributed and two hundred and eighty five (285) were retrieved of which two hundred and seven one (271) copies were found useable. This gives a response rate of 95.8 percent. Only 89.7 percent of the administered questionnaire was found useable. The responses were coded and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 20.0) was used to run data analysis.

Hypothesis One

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 2:

Table 1: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.640	5.645	0.000	Significant	0.917	0.840	0.840	1875.954, p<0.05
Pq	1.095	43.312	0.000	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=C

Source: Computed by the Researcher, (2023)

In testing the hypothesis, perceived quality was regressed against consumption. The result of the simple regression analysis showed the model to examine the effect of perceived quality on consumption. **Consumption = 0.640 + 1.095Pq**. The result showed that the coefficient of perceived quality had positive effect on consumption. This means that perceived quality has positive and direct effect on consumption. The results of the t – statistic denotes that the coefficient was statistically significance because observed values of t – statistic (43.312) was greater than its P-values (0.000). The results of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis one was statistically significance because observed value of the F – statistic (1875.954) was greater than its p-value (0.000).

Hypothesis Two

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 3:

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.650	6.401	0.000	Significant	0.932	0.869	0.868	2351.338, p<0.05
Pq	1.109	48.491	0.000	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=C

Source: Computed by the Researcher, (2023)

In testing the hypothesis, Perceived globalness (Pq) were regressed against consumption. The result of the simple regression analysis showed the model to examine the effect of Perceived globalness on consumption. **Consumption= 0.640 + 1.109Pq**. The result showed that the coefficient of perceived globalness had positive effect on consumption. This means that Perceived globalness has positive and direct effect on consumption. The results of the t – statistic denotes that the coefficient was statistically significance because observed values of t – statistic (48.491) was greater than its P-values (0.000). The results of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis two was statistically significance because observed value of the F – statistic (2351.338) was greater than its p-value (0.000). The result means that the strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that perceived globalness had a significant effect on consumption.

Hypothesis Three

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 4:

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.195	2.275	0.024	Significant	0.941	0.885	0.884	2734.409, p<0.05
Pu	1.015	52.292	0.000	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=C

Source: Computed by the Researcher, (2023)

In testing the hypothesis, perceived uniqueness was regressed against consumption. The result of the simple regression analysis showed the model to examine the effect of perceived uniqueness on consumer purchase behaviour on consumption. **Consumption= 0.640 + 1.015Pu**. The result showed that the coefficient of perceived uniqueness had positive effect on consumption. This means that perceived uniqueness has positive and direct effect on consumption. The results of the t – statistic denotes that the coefficient was statistically significance because observed values of t – statistic (42.292) was greater than its P-values (0.000). The results of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis one was statistically significance because observed value of the F – statistic (2734.409) was greater than its p-value (0.000). The strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary

This study examined the effect of perceived quality on electronic marketing and the marketing performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. A total of 296 respondents from Calabar were selected for the study. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which served as the primary instrument for gathering relevant information.

- i. The first null hypothesis stated that there is no significant effect of perceived quality on consumption. Findings showed that there is a positive relationship between perceived quality and consumption.
- ii. The second null hypothesis also stated that there is no significant relationship between perceived globalness and consumption. Findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between perceived globalness and consumption.
- iii. The third null hypothesis stated that there is no significant effect of perceived uniqueness and consumption. Findings showed that there is a positive relationship between perceived uniqueness and consumption.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, certainly, customer perception can directly affect consumption especially as it concerns made in Nigeria products. The researcher further concluded that the consumption rate to a large extent depends on customer perception of a brand.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Manufacturers should ensure that their brands and products are not prone to complications, dents, fading, and losing colours to enhance the trust of their customers.
- ii. Local manufacturers should strive to penetrate the international market to make their products a global product.
- iii. Nigerian manufacturers should also strive for excellence in the uniqueness of Made in Nigeria products concerning their brands to compete successfully against foreign competitors.

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